

WORKPLAN

for the research stay of Lemenkova Polina, M.Sc.,
during the time span 01st January 2012 - 30th June 2012 (six months)
at the *Eötvös Loránd University (ELTE), Faculty of Informatics,*
Department of Cartography and Geoinformatics.

Spatial GIS Analysis of the Environmental Landscape Changes, Hungary

1. Introduction: research problem

The landscape has been changed in Hungary in recent years due to the environmental change, amended agricultural practices and housing development. The Google Earth aerial photographs and Landsat TM scenes provide an important record of the landscape at the current moment as well as giving a retrospective assessment for the past, against which future changes can be analysed, monitored and possible development discussed. Comparison of up-to-date landscapes with those on older (up to 20 years old) photography allows us to assess changes which have taken place in recent decade both qualitatively (which land use areas disappeared and which expanded their area) and quantitatively (exact estimation of the area in km² and its accuracy).

Using various geospatial data from different sources (see below) we are going to assess changes in the landscape structure of Hungary. The main character of this work is thus GIS-based environmental assessment of the Hungarian landscapes.

2. Technical approach: data and software to be used

The proposed research work is suggested to be technically based on the following instruments and data. The main software that will be used is GIS: GRASS, ILWIS, Quantum GIS. Other auxiliary tools and additional software may be used in the working process, depending on needs (Global Mapper, ERDAS Imagine).

The spatial analysis of land cover patterns is suggested to be studied using images processing based on the available open sources: satellite imagery from USGS (<http://www.usgs.gov/pubprod/>), The Earth Science Data Interface (<http://glcfapp.glc.f.umd.edu:8080/esdi/index.jsp>), GloVis (<http://glovis.usgs.gov/>), as well as Google Earth aerial images, free DEMs (from the open source <http://geomorphometry.org/content/data-sets>), vector maps or any other available data.

The research data pool is suggested to be most up-to-date, covering period of approximately 10-20 years: since 1990- early 2000-s up to the latest time, depending on the availability.

For the DCW data (hydrography) we will also consider useful source of Geocommunity (<http://data.geocomm.com/>), Natural Earth data <http://www.naturalearthdata.com> and <http://www.fao.org/geonetwork/srv/en/main.home> Other additional available spatial geodata sources will be considered during the research work.

3. **Aims and objectives**

The research aims to apply methods of spatial analysis based on open source GIS software (GRASS and ILWIS, also Erdas Imagine for images classification). The main objective of the research is mapping the land cover types and quantitative estimation of their areas in Hungary. We also intend to investigate possible impact of the environmental changes on the Hungarian ecozones: biodiversity change detection.

The spatial analysis includes classification of the research area into different ecozones by means of the analysis of geomorphological and environmental conditions. Namely, at this working step we intend to incorporate various sources of data into the GIS project: use DEMs for geomorphological analysis, results of images classification with determined land cover types, plus vector map layers. The integration of data will enable us to investigate spatially single land cover patterns within the general structure of physical-geographic characteristics of Hungary.

The temporal dynamics of the environmental changes will be based on the supervised classification and investigation of the land cover types distribution. The differences between various classes on the images will be detected using various bands combinations on the masked Landsat images. The detected changes will be studied for the exact estimation of the changes in various landscapes.

Spatial analysis of the landscape structure in Hungary will help to highlight adaptation of its different ecoregions towards the changing environment: which regions undergone any changes and are, therefore, most environmentally vulnerable and have lesser resistance capability towards global climate change. The detection of the land cover expansion or reduction will display areas with the most rapid changes in the landscape structure of Hungary.

4. **Time schedule**

01.January – 01 February 2012: Data collecting and treatment (organising GIS project)

01 February–01 March 2012: Data management and administration (georeferencing and adjusting all data to common format; start of data manipulating)

01 March – 01 April 2012: Environmental analysis and GIS main work; monitoring of land cover types; images classification.

01 April – 01 May 2012: Environmental analysis and GIS main work (continue); assessment of landscape changes

01 May – 01 June 2012: Mapping the results (preparing the final layouts), and writing an article, reporting the results, for an international peer-review geographic journal

01 June – 30 June 2012: Publishing results; preparing the report with results of the research work for *Hungarian State Scholarship Board (HSB)*

5. **Expected results**

We suggest the final outcome of the proposed research work to include following cartographic results:

- Small-scaled thematic analytical map showing actual general structure of the geography of Hungary: its geomorphological sketch (3D visualisation using available DEM), combined with thematic layers showing land cover types in Hungary nowadays.
- Map of the land cover types which should include various geographic regions of Hungary and display the areas with landscape changes.
- The zonal middle-scale maps of the spatial distribution of ecoregions over various areas of Hungary are planned to illustrate current situation in the landscape structure of the country. Here we plan to map three major geographic regions:
 - 1) Montane part consisting of Transdanubian Medium Mountains, Transdanubian Hills and Mecsek Mountains
 - 2) Plain region of Great Hungarian Plain, or Great Alföld and its surroundings
- Visualisation of the selected areas of physical geography of Hungary in more detailed scale. Here we will highlight the areas of special interests, mapped more detailed depending on the available data. These areas include regions with most rapid or evident changes, and we plan to investigate them more detailed.
- In case if there are any proved detected changes in land cover types: statistical outcome estimating the environmentally changed areas. These results will include tables displaying calculations or areas.

6. **Significance**

- The proposed research work will be an important scientific contribution to the studies of Hungarian and European environmental biodiversity and nature conservation.
- Technically, we will apply various open source methods and tools, and thus explore the possibilities of the GRASS and ILWIS towards landscape mapping and spatial analysis.
- The suggested methodology of the spatial analysis and environmental mapping of the landscapes can be applied towards other areas with similar landscape structure.

7. **Keywords**

Hungary, environmental changes, spatial analysis, GRASS GIS, ILWIS, images classification, land cover types, landscape ecoregions.